

Fiber-artefact methodology and calibration framework for Brillouin-based fiber sensing

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Abstract: We propose, and demonstrate, the use of a fiber-optical measurement artefact as a metrological tool for traceable distance calibration of distributed optical fiber sensors. The constructed fiber artefact consists of a lead-in fiber coupled to a fiber loop using a 3-dB coupler and is used to calibrate both a home-built Brillouin-OTDR setup and a custom version of a commercial Brillouin-OTDR interrogator build for distributed temperature sensing. For both interrogators, we demonstrate distance calibrations with 1-meter uncertainty ($k=1$) in the offset length and 0.1 % (1 m/km) uncertainty ($k = 1$) in the distance scale factor. In addition, it is shown that the fiber artefact can be used to assess undesired distance-dependent measurement biases.

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1. Introduction

Distributed optical fiber sensing (DOFS) is a disruptive technology which has matured significantly in the past decade [1–3]. With inherent advantages such as simultaneous large spatial coverage and high sensor-point density, electro-magnetic immunity, and long lifetime, the different shapes and forms of DOFS provide unique solutions to various real-world monitoring- and sensing challenges [4–6]. Applications include fire detection and heat monitoring in tunnels [7], high-temperature sensing at nuclear power plants [8], dynamic load assessment of high-voltage power cables [9], acoustic monitoring of power transformers [10], seismic event detection [11], road- and structural health monitoring [12,13], high pressure vessel safety enhancement [14], and subsea acoustic sensor networks [15].

Despite many of the applications listed above relating to critical infrastructure, the regulatory requirements of the sensing devices, commonly referred to as interrogators, remain very limited. In addition, metrological infrastructure at third-party laboratories, such as national metrology institutes, is currently missing, leaving quality assurance and calibration assessment in the hands of the manufacturers. This potentially leads to inconsistencies between measurement setups which will undermine user confidence in the instrumentation. Fortunately, efforts to address this issue are gaining momentum, with a growing emphasis on standardization [16,17] and the development of industry standards by SEAFOM working groups.

The establishment of metrological infrastructure for third-party testing and calibration of commercial DOFS solutions, involves developing methodologies and procedures that can

serve as the foundation for international standards. For DOFS, this requires a framework that enables simultaneous assessment of all the different metrics that need to be calibrated, such as measurement accuracy and repeatability, spatial uncertainty and resolution, and working range. Numerous previous studies have addressed the metrological challenge of calibrating distributed optical fiber sensors [18–25]. In this work, we introduce and demonstrate the new concept of a fiber-optical artefact to assess interrogators based on Brillouin optical time-domain reflectometry (BOTDR) for distributed temperature sensing (DTS). Our developed method enables traceable calibration of interrogator spatial uncertainty (distance), which is an aspect that has largely been overlooked by the community but must be included in a combined metrological framework. Additionally, the developed methodology provides a unique approach for assessing whether the interrogator-under-test suffers from undesired distance-dependent measurement biases.

2. Methodology of the fiber artefact

2.1. Fiber-artefact architecture

The proposed fiber-optical artefact is inspired by a similar standard within regular OTDR length calibration [26], and its modified architecture is sketched in Fig. 1(a). The fiber artefact consists of two separate single-mode fiber sections connected to a polarization insensitive 3-dB splitter and a polarization insensitive 3-port circulator in a loop-configuration. The two separate fiber sections are referred to as the lead-in fiber and the loop fiber and have nominal lengths L_A and L_B , respectively. The idea behind the fiber artefact is that it can be used as a length transfer standard, for which the lengths L_A and L_B are to be traceably measured with low uncertainty (see subsection 2.3). Measuring on the fiber artefact with a DOFS interrogator, such as a BOTDR device, subsequently enables the spatial accuracy of the interrogator to be calibrated (see section 3).

Fig. 1. Proposed fiber artefact for distributed optical fiber sensing. (a) Sketch of the fiber artefact architecture consisting of a lead-in fiber, a 3-dB coupler, a loop fiber, and a circulator (b) Exemplification of retrieved signal-strength profile (top) and measurand trace (bottom) visualizing both the periodicity of the loop and the measurement dead zones that arise due to the in-loop circulator functioning as an isolator.

The modified fiber artefact architecture proposed here, deviates from regular OTDR artefacts through the inclusion of the in-loop circulator, which critically divides the loop fiber into two subsections of lengths L_{B1} (before the circulator) and L_{B2} (after the circulator). The two loop sections are constrained by $L_{B2} > L_{B1}$ to prevent ambiguity between backscattered light arriving simultaneously at the interrogator from two distinct spatial points in the loop. This is ensured by the circulator, which allows the interrogating probe pulses to repetitively probe fiber loop in the counter clockwise direction, while preventing Brillouin backscatter from the second part of the loop. Thus, the circulator functions as an isolator in the case of BOTDR interrogation, and in

other configurations, such as Brillouin optical time domain analysis, the circulator may be used as entrance point for the counter-propagating light field. Figure 1(b) illustrates sketched versions of expected backscattering strength with the expected semi-periodicity of the measurand and the measurement "dead zones" that arise due to the positioning of the in-loop circulator (isolator). It must be noted that the repetition rate of the interrogator device has to be set low enough that consecutive probe pulses do not interrogate the fiber loop simultaneously.

The assembled fiber artefact consists of SMF-28e (Corning) standard optical telecommunication fiber in all three sections. This type of fiber has a single isolated Brillouin peak at approximately 10.85 GHz simplifying data acquisition and -processing. The three separate fiber sections have approximate lengths: $L_A \approx 170$ m, $L_{B_1} \approx 250$ m, and $L_{B_2} \approx 1000$ m. The exact fiber lengths are not crucially important, but it should be mentioned that the length of the loop fiber L_B is approximately inversely proportional to the resulting calibration uncertainty of the interrogator distance scale factor (see section 3.1). Thus, the loop length of around 1250 m, was chosen as a compromise between achieving a low calibration uncertainty while maintaining a significant signal-to-noise ratio after multiple loop round trips.

In addition to playing the role of a length transfer standard, the fiber artefact architecture uniquely allows each individual probe pulse to repetitively interrogate the same fiber section inside the loop. This enables testing of potential distance-dependent measurement biases that may arise as a result of poor pulse extinction ratios and the decreasing signal-to-noise ratio as a function of round-trip number (see subsection 3.2). The artefact could therefore serve as a metrological performance standard.

2.2. Fiber-artefact interrogation

Our interrogator, sketched in Fig. 2, is a custom-build BOTDR setup that employs coherent detection with a 12-GHz photoreceiver (Optilab, PR-12-B-M). The interrogating probe pulses originate from a 1542-nm CW fiber laser (NKT Photonics, Koheras Adjustik), which are carved using a pulse generator (Highland Technology, J270) feeding a high-extinction ratio (>40 dB) intensity modulator (Exail Photonics, MXER) actively bias-controlled to achieve minimum optical transmission. Real-time data acquisition is achieved using an FPGA (Red Pitaya, STEMLab 125-14) which, at a sampling rate of 125 Msps/s and a 60-MHz measurement bandwidth, measures the mean absolute voltage of the intermediate-frequency signal that has been down-mixed by a tunable electrical local oscillator (Windfreak Technologies, SynthHD Mini). Data is chunk-wise automatically offloaded to a separate processor for storage, post-processing, model fitting, and visualization.

Figure 3(a) shows a BOTDR trace for a performed interrogation of the assembled fiber artefact. Each data point represents the average Brillouin center frequency (estimator: $\hat{\nu}_B$) from 4 individual interrogation runs. The corresponding error bars, shown in Fig. 3(b), signify the expanded measurement uncertainty ($U(\hat{\nu}_B)$) calculated using a coverage factor of 3.3, which provides a 95% confidence level at 3 degrees of freedom. The uncertainty values are dominated by random measurement errors, although small environmental changes were sometimes observed between runs, particularly in the lead-in fiber section with low measurement noise. The interrogation trace is, as expected, seen to be divided into separate sections consisting of the lead-in fiber, the first part of the loop fiber, and the dead zone. The Brillouin fingerprint of the loop fiber is repeatedly seen as the probe pulse circulates the fiber loop, and the measurement uncertainty naturally increases for each round trip due to a round-trip loss of 4.2 dB (primarily due to the 3-dB splitter). The Brillouin fingerprint pattern of the loop fiber repeats itself at a spatial frequency of $2/L_B$ as the Brillouin-scattered light does not circulate in the loop.

3. Brillouin-OTDR distance calibration

3.1. Spatial accuracy of a Brillouin-OTDR device

3.1.1. General framework

Analogously to the case of a regular OTDR device [26], the distance calibration of a BOTDR interrogator involves determination of two parameters: the location offset, L_0 (ideally 0), and the distance scale factor, S_L (ideally 1). These two calibration parameters characterize the spatial accuracy of the BOTDR instrument, and are found through linear regression analysis using a model function of the form $z_{\text{Meas}} = S_L z_{\text{Ref}} + L_0$. Here, z_{Ref} represents the calibrated length values of the fiber artefact from Table 1 and z_{Meas} are the corresponding BOTDR distance values found below. The model function also highlights the advantage of using the fiber loop artefact as the length standard, as it allows calibration of both L_0 and S_L in a single interrogation run.

Table 1. Time-of-flight calibration results of the lead-in fiber length L_A and the loop-fiber length^a

Lead-in fiber, L_A	Loop fiber, L_B
$z_{\text{Ref}}^{(1)}$ (m)	$z_{\text{Ref}}^{(2)}$ (m)
173.6(0.3)	1275.6(0.3)

^aStandard uncertainty values ($k = 1$) are provided in parentheses.

3.1.2. Determining the BOTDR distance points

To illustrate how the BOTDR distance values, z_{Meas} , are assigned, Fig. 4 shows select zoomed-in versions of BOTDR traces after (a) the lead-in fiber (b) one round trip in the loop, and (c) two round trips in the loop. Interrogation traces are shown for three separate runs using probe pulses of respectively 30 ns, 50 ns, and 100 ns, and they illustrate how the Brillouin center frequency changes across the 3-dB coupler region. As expected, the shorter probe pulses are better at resolving the Brillouin feature of the short 3-dB coupling device. The distance assignment must represent the end of the coupler as in the case of the time-of-flight calibration presented in Sec. 2.3. The readout of these locations is in principle best performed using a trace showing the evolution of the residual sum of squares (RSS) of the Brillouin center-frequency fits. However, RSS values are not available as outputs from commercial interrogators, which prevents this use in practice. Instead, we exploit the Brillouin feature of the 3-dB coupler region to perform distance allocations. The allocations, illustrated by the encircled data points, follow the rule of a local minimum

$$\hat{v}_B^{(n-1)} > \hat{v}_B^{(n)} < \hat{v}_B^{(n+1)}, \quad (1)$$

where n is the sample number for the distance z_n . Notably, this allocation method does not apply universally. However, with the Brillouin feature of the coupler in use, the chosen data points represent the last location before the probe pulse has propagated through the coupling fiber section and fully into the loop fiber section at distances of approximately 176 m, 815 m, and 1453 m.

The distance allocations found by the method above naturally result in a pulse-width-dependent bias as a longer pulse takes more time to propagate fully through the coupler region. This bias must be corrected for to provide pulse-width independent calibration of the interrogator. For example a closer look at Fig. 4(a) show distance assignments of $z_{30\text{ns}}^{(1)} \approx 172.6$ m, $z_{50\text{ns}}^{(1)} \approx 174.0$ m, and $z_{100\text{ns}}^{(1)} \approx 176.3$ m, demonstrating a clear pulse width dependence. A correction of $-\Delta t c / (4 \times 1.46)$ (or $-\Delta t c / (2 \times 1.46)$ without previous use of center-offset correction) must be applied to arrive

Fig. 4. Visualization of BOTDR distance assignments (encircled data points) for three different fiber-artefact distances: (a) after the lead-in fiber, (b) after one loop round trip, and (c) after two loop round trips. The three different datasets correspond to pulse durations of 30 ns (blue crosses), 50 ns (orange circles), and 100 ns (green squares). The error bars represent expanded uncertainties at the 95% confidence level.

at an unbiased distance estimate, resulting in the values $\hat{z}_{30\text{ns}}^{(1)} \approx 171.0$ m, $\hat{z}_{50\text{ns}}^{(1)} \approx 171.4$ m, and $\hat{z}_{100\text{ns}}^{(1)} \approx 171.2$ m, which is in mutual agreement considering the sampling resolution of 0.82 m.

3.1.3. Brillouin-OTDR autocorrelation trace

With the procedure above, we are left with relatively few points (3) for performing regression analysis. Fortunately, the repetitive pattern of $\hat{\nu}_B(z)$ already observed in Fig. 3 allows for an estimation of the half loop length $L_B/2$. These estimates are obtained using the autocorrelation function $\rho_{\nu_B}(\Delta z)$ for which peaks are expected at integers of $\Delta z = L_B/2$ due to $\hat{\nu}_B(z) \sim \hat{\nu}_B(z + L_B/2)$ for $z > L_A$. This is illustrated graphically in Fig. 5(a-c), showing the computed autocorrelation traces, $\rho_{\nu_B}(\Delta z)$, for interrogation runs using the three pulse durations of 30 ns, 50 ns, and 100 ns. The most prominent peaks are found at $\Delta z = (637.4 \pm 1.0)$ m in all three cases, as anticipated from the calibration result of the loop fiber in Table 1. It should be noted that this method of utilizing the autocorrelation trace to determine the loop-length works poorly if L_{B_1} (the first part of the loop from which a signal is retrieved) is too short compared to L_{B_2} (the second part of the loop from which a signal is not retrieved). If $L_{B_2} \gg L_{B_1}$ the dead-zone (of length $L_{B_2}/2 - L_{B_1}/2$), for which the estimate of ν_B is dominated by noise (suppressed in Fig. 3 for visual

Fig. 5. Autocorrelation of $\hat{\nu}_B(z)$ using different pulse durations of 30 ns (top), 50 ns (middle), and 100 ns (bottom). In all three instances, strong correlation is observed for a spatial delay of $\Delta z \approx 637.5$ m representing half the length of the loop fiber.

purposes), becomes even larger in comparison to the sensed portion of the fiber loop. This in turn renders the autocorrelation useless as it becomes dominated by noise at the relevant spatial delays. For the same reason, it is beneficial to restrict the range of distances used for computing the autocorrelation. The best results are achieved by excluding data from the lead-in fiber and data beyond a certain length, typically after approximately four loop round trips, depending on the signal-to-noise ratio.

3.1.4. Brillouin-OTDR distance calibration using general least-squares

The BOTDR calibration results of the preceding two sections are gathered in Table 2 along with the accompanying uncertainties that have contributions from; (i) sampling, (ii) accuracy of spatial resolution, (iii) environmental uncertainty due to changes in optical-fiber temperature, (iv) and accuracy of the laser wavelength. These results form the basis for finding the sought after calibration values ($L_0, u(L_0)$) and ($S_L, u(S_L)$).

Table 2. BOTDR distance calibration using the fiber calibration artefact

Pulse width (ns)	Distance allocations			
	$z_{\text{Meas}}^{(1)}$ (m)	$z_{\text{Meas}}^{(2)}$ (m)	$z_{\text{Meas}}^{(3)}$ (m)	$z_{\text{Meas}}^{(4)}$ (m)
30	171.0(0.9)	637.4(1.0)	809.2(0.9)	1447.4(0.9)
50	171.4(1.0)	637.4(1.0)	809.6(1.0)	1447.8(1.0)
100	171.2(1.0)	637.4(1.0)	809.4(1.0)	1447.6(1.0)

To achieve this, we use the general least-squares framework [27], in which our ($m = 6$) measurands $\mathbf{z} = (z_{\text{Ref}}^{(1)}, z_{\text{Ref}}^{(2)}, z_{\text{Meas}}^{(1)}, z_{\text{Meas}}^{(2)}, z_{\text{Meas}}^{(3)}, z_{\text{Meas}}^{(4)})^T$ are considered estimates of the "true" values $\boldsymbol{\zeta} = (\zeta_{\text{Ref}}^{(1)}, \zeta_{\text{Ref}}^{(2)}, \zeta_{\text{Meas}}^{(1)}, \zeta_{\text{Meas}}^{(2)}, \zeta_{\text{Meas}}^{(3)}, \zeta_{\text{Meas}}^{(4)})^T$. Least-squares estimates of the true values $\hat{\boldsymbol{\zeta}}$ and the model parameters, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} = (\hat{L}_0, \hat{S}_L)^T$, are obtained through minimization of the chi-squared function

$$\chi^2(\mathbf{z}, \boldsymbol{\zeta}) = (\mathbf{z} - \boldsymbol{\zeta})^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1} (\mathbf{z} - \boldsymbol{\zeta}), \quad \boldsymbol{\Sigma} = u(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}^T), \quad (2)$$

subject to the constraints set by the four following implicit equations

$$\mathbf{f}_{\boldsymbol{\beta}}(\boldsymbol{\zeta}) = \begin{pmatrix} S_L \zeta_{\text{Ref}}^{(1)} + L_0 - \zeta_{\text{Meas}}^{(1)} \\ S_L \zeta_{\text{Ref}}^{(2)} / 2 - \zeta_{\text{Meas}}^{(2)} \\ S_L \left(\zeta_{\text{Ref}}^{(1)} + \zeta_{\text{Ref}}^{(2)} / 2 \right) + L_0 - \zeta_{\text{Meas}}^{(3)} \\ S_L \left(\zeta_{\text{Ref}}^{(1)} + \zeta_{\text{Ref}}^{(2)} \right) + L_0 - \zeta_{\text{Meas}}^{(4)} \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{0}. \quad (3)$$

This constrained minimisation problem can be solved by employing Lagrange multipliers, the details of which can be found in [27].

Note the subtlety in the second line of Eq. (3) which does not contain the location-offset contribution L_0 as the measurement value $z_{\text{Meas}}^{(2)}$ was obtained through use of the trace autocorrelation function which is independent of the location offset. As a result, we are unable to construct a simple linear model, which in turn prevents the implementation of an ordinary least squares approach. An alternative to the method outlined above would be to treat the problem using a version of constrained least squares with the second equation imposing a requirement on the slope S_L . The two methods should yield near identical outcomes, however, the employed method is chosen as it is in full compliance with the GUM.

The results of the least-squares fits are summarized in Table 3, including values for \hat{L}_0 , \hat{S}_L , $u(\hat{L}_0)$, $u(\hat{S}_L)$, and the probability $P(\chi^2(2) > \chi_{\min}^2)$, where χ_{\min}^2 is the found minimum chi-squared

Table 3. Summary of the general-least squares calibration results yielding estimated values for the location offset L_0 and the distance scale factor S_L

Pulse width (ns)	Least squares results summary		
	\hat{L}_0 (m)	\hat{S}_L	$P(\chi^2 > \chi^2_{\min})$
30	-2.41(0.89)	1.0005(0.0009)	0.80
50	-1.97(0.97)	1.0005(0.0009)	0.81
100	-2.17(0.97)	1.0004(0.0010)	0.81

value, and $\chi^2(2)$ is the chi-squared distribution with $\nu = 2$ degrees of freedom. Values of around 0.8 indicate that the model provides a good fit to the measurements including their uncertainties.

The slope estimates \hat{S}_L contain the unit value within the ($k = 1$) confidence intervals $\hat{S}_L \pm u(\hat{S}_L)$. In reality this is primarily a test of the interrogators timing accuracy and a check for software errors. On the other hand, the location offset estimates \hat{L}_0 are found to statistically differ from zero at the 2σ -confidence level as $\hat{L}_0 + 2u(\hat{L}_0) < 0$. This discrepancy is, however, expected as the custom-build BOTDR interrogator was not calibrated prior to the measurements. The fiber artefact can thereby be used to software-adjust for non-zero location offsets in much the same way a weighing scale can be zeroed.

3.2. Distance-dependent measurement bias

The architecture of the fiber artefact enables repetitive sampling of the same fiber section within the life cycle of every individual probe pulse. In addition to the opportunity this provides for interrogator distance calibration, it therefore also enables a unique method for quantifying the distance dependency of the measured Brillouin center frequency. Such a dependency will typically be a result of poor pulse-to-background extinction ratio but can also stem from imperfect square pulse shapes [28] and self-phase-modulation induced frequency chirps [29].

Fig. 6. Differential averaged Brillouin center frequency, $\Delta\bar{\nu}_B$, as a function of round trip number in the fiber loop.

To investigate this dependence, BOTDR interrogation of the fiber artefact was carried out for six different probe pulse durations (varying from 20 ns to 100 ns). The average Brillouin center frequency $\bar{\nu}_B$ was computed for each round trip N , starting from the respective distance allocations (see Fig. 4). The average value obtained from the first round trip was used as a reference to calculate the change $\Delta\bar{\nu}_B(N) = \bar{\nu}_B(N) - \bar{\nu}_B(1)$, which is shown in Fig. 6. The error bars ($k = 2$) originate in part from repetitive experiments and in part from dividing the fiber loop section into individual subsections over which the averages are computed. The data clearly demonstrate a decrease in the Brillouin center frequency as a function of N . This tendency is only barely evident after the second round trip but is clearly seen for the third. Moreover, the

tendency becomes more pronounced with decreasing pulse duration ($\Delta\bar{\nu}_B(3) \approx -1.5$ MHz for a pulse duration of 20 ns versus $\Delta\bar{\nu}_B(3) \approx -0.7$ MHz for 100 ns), which is not unexpected with our limited extinction ratio of ~ 40 dB. This demonstrates that the developed fiber artefact is capable of revealing potential issues with distance-dependent and pulse-length dependent measurement biases.

3.3. Distance calibration of commercial interrogator

As a final test, we used a custom-build version of commercial DTS equipment (OTS4, LUNA Innovations) to interrogate the fiber artefact. Measurements were performed at three different settings for spatial resolution at 3 m, 5 m, and 10 m to resemble the experiments performed using our in-house interrogator. Distance allocations and autocorrelation-based loop-length estimation were performed following the same procedure as outlined above. The spatial calibration results for the OTS4 DTS system are summarized in the left part of Table 4. Whereas the distance scale factor, S_L , is found to differ insignificantly from unity as desired, the location offset, L_0 , was found to be approximately -30 m. This discrepancy turned out to originate from a user-defined configuration setting of the device, which was used with emphasis on ultra long distance (~ 250 km) measurements [30]. Notably, we also find that the L_0 value obtained for the 10-m resolution setting deviates from the value obtained for the other two settings. It was in general not as easy to make the allocations based on Eq. (1) for the commercial interrogator, especially for the 10-m setting, which might have caused this discrepancy. In a modified version of the fiber artefact, this issue may be alleviated by incorporating a fiber piece with a different Brillouin frequency in the beginning of the fiber loop.”

Secondly, the distance-dependent measurement bias was also investigated for the OTS4 interrogator with results tabulated in the right part of Table 4. Contrary to what was observed for the home-build BOTDR interrogator, the OTS4 device exhibits no tendency in terms of distance-dependent measurement bias for any of the three resolution settings.

Table 4. Spatial calibration results and distance-dependent measurement biases obtained for the commercial BOTDR interrogator

Resolution setting (m)	Least squares summary		Distance bias	
	\hat{L}_0 (m)	\hat{S}_L	$\Delta\bar{\nu}_B(2)$ (MHz)	$\Delta\bar{\nu}_B(3)$ (MHz)
3	-34.8(1.0)	0.9991(0.0009)	0.08(0.08)	0.04(0.28)
5	-35.3(1.0)	1.0001(0.0009)	0.11(0.06)	-0.07(0.16)
10	-30.6(1.0)	0.9989(0.0009)	0.02(0.03)	0.01(0.07)

4. Conclusion

We have introduced and demonstrated the concept of a loop-based fiber artefact with the purpose of establishing a metrological calibration framework within distributed optical fiber sensing. The fiber artefact enables traceable calibration of the spatial uncertainty of distributed interrogator systems, and may be used to assess undesired effects such as distance-dependent measurement biases. The fiber artefact has been initially developed for Brillouin-based fiber-optical sensing, but may be generalized to Rayleigh- and Raman based distributed sensors with relatively small adjustments.

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Data availability. Data is available upon request to the corresponding author.

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